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Palm Wine Mixed Culture Fermentation Kinetics

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a mathematical model was developed describing the mixed culture fermentation of palm juice based on the growth profiles of the four microorganisms found in the juice. These microorganisms are *Yeast*, *Micrococcus*, *Lactic acid bacteria* and *Leuconostoc spp.* The mathematical model was simulated using MATLAB which showed the relationship between the substrate concentration and time for the individual microorganisms.

Experimental data obtained from literature was used to obtain the growth rates and substrate saturation coefficient using the Monod model. It can be seen that the cell number of *Leuconostoc spp.* has increased to 1978.3 while the experimental value is 1667.0678 at 24hours. The substrate concentration at 24hrs was found to be 4.968g/100g dry matter while its experimental value is 4.348g/100g dry matter. This shows that there is a reasonable level of accuracy in the model developed.

Keywords: Fermentation, kinetics, micro flora, mixed culture, yeast.

INTRODUCTION

Brief History of Palm Juice

Palm-wine is an important alcoholic beverage resulting from the spontaneous fermentation of the sap of the palm, which has been attributed to yeasts and bacteria (Okafor, 1978). Fermented palm-juice is an exudate from palm-tree. Natural palm sap is collected from the oil palm tree *Elaeis guineenses* and the raphia palms, *Raphia hookeri* and *Raphia vinifera*, although it could also be obtained from other species of palm trees that are known all over the world. Palm wine is produced when the inflorescence of the palm tree is incised and tapped, which is collected in a calabash that is hung at the base of the incision. Fresh palm-wine is sweet, clear, neutral, colorless juice containing 10-12% sucrose, minimal invert sugar (less than 0.5%), small amounts of proteins, gums and mineral.

(Okafor, 1987). Spontaneous fermentation starts immediately the sap is collected and within an hour or two becomes reasonably high in alcohol (up to 4%) (Bassir, 1962). Organisms responsible include *S. cerevisiae* and *schizosaccharomyces pombe*, and the bacteria *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *L. mesenteroids* (Okafor, 1987).

The equations of reaction of fermentation of palm-wine and oxidation of ethanol are represented thus respectively;

In the former fermentation process, ethanol is produced as the sugar content diminishes rapidly as it is acted upon by agents of fermentation (microorganisms) while in the latter, ethanol will be on the declining phase as it is converted to acetic acid in conditions of excess oxygen.

Mixed Culture Fermentation

Mixed culture fermentation is a biochemical process involving two or more microorganisms in a nutrient substance in specially controlled conditions for scientific, medical or commercial purposes (Microsoft Encarta, 2004). The interactions of mixed culture systems are difficult to interpret because there is no good reference point when so many conditions and concentrations may be changing at once.

Research Objective

The purposes of this research are:

- To obtain from literature the microorganisms that proliferates during the mixed-culture fermentation of palm wine.
- To determine the process conditions for the fermentation.
- To determine the yield coefficients of the respective micro-organisms in the fermentation process with respect to time.
- To estimate kinetic parameters of the microorganisms present based on reliable experimental data from literature.
- To determine the substrate utilization profile from the start of fermentation (0th hour) to the end of fermentation (72nd hour) at intervals of two hours.
- To write a mathematical model that describes the process, this will be an aid to Biochemical and Chemical Engineers in designing a large-scale fermenter of the process.
- To write a computer program that will solve the mathematical model and simulate the process.

Microorganisms Responsible for Fermentation

Studies on the microbiology of palm wine have shown that palm wine contain both yeast and bacteria (Okafor, 1978).

Yeast

Okafor (1978) isolated and identified yeasts from palm wine from various parts of Nigeria and concluded that the distribution of yeast in palm wine is not dictated by the type of palm or the locality in which it grows. In his study, all the samples were dominated by *saccharomyces* and *candida* irrespective of the type of palm or the area in which it is grown.

Bacteria

Bacteria encountered in palm wine include *Lactobacillus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Bacillus*, *Serratic*, *Streptococcus*, *Zymomonas mobilis*, *Micrococcus*, *Breviabacterium*, *Pediococcus*, *Corynebacterium*, *Klebsiella* (Bassir, 1962; Faparusi, 1966).

SUCCESSION of MICRO FLORA DURING FERMENTATION

In this regard, Bassir and Faparusi (1971) reported the presence of *Lactobacillus* and *Leuconostoc* in the early stages of fermentation. Okafor (1975) found that while lactic acid bacteria as a group were important, there were no consistent patterns of the distribution of the various *lactic*. According to him, *streptococcus* was found throughout the 7days period he carried out his work whereas *lactobacillus* remained only during the first 3 days of fermentation.

Okafor (1975) reported the presence of *enterobacteriaceae* such as *serratia* and *klebsiella* early in fermentation. According to him, *yeasts* and *micrococcus* seem to occur consistently in many samples of palm wine. Faparusi and Bassir (1971) also reported the same in their investigations.

Authorities who have studied the succession of micro flora in palm wine consistently reported the emergence of *Acetobacter* after about 2 to 3 days of fermentation, at which time; alcohol was present in reasonable quantities (Faparusi and Bassir, 1971; Okafor, 1975).

Factors Affecting Rate of Fermentation

Despite its complexity, the rate of fermentation is largely dependent upon certain parameters namely yeast, wort composition (i.e. Fermentable filtrates normally nutrients for yeast) and the processing condition such as time, temperature, volume, vessel shape and size, pH, acid, water activity, carbon sources are also complementary variables. These conditions are in general applied to all classes of fermentation, be it batch process or the continuous process.

Fermentation Process

In fermentation, an accurate mathematical model is a prerequisite for the control, optimization and the simulation of a process. The kinetics for growth is generally modeled as first order. A batch fermentation process such as that for palm wine has a growth rate equation modeled as

$$\frac{dX_i}{dt} = \mu_i X_i \quad (1.1)$$

Where

X_i = concentration (cell number) of the i th organism
 μ_i = specific growth rate of the i th organism
 t = time

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{\mu X_i}{Y_i} \quad (1.2)$$

Where

S = Substrate concentration
 Y = yield coefficient for individual organism

The assumption made in generating this model is simply that the organisms compete for the common substrate without preying on one another. This can be used as an analogy for the mixed culture fermentation of palm juice as there are no serious prey-predator relationships among the organism.

The growth rate, μ takes the form

$$\mu_i = \frac{\mu_{i,max} S}{k_m + S} \quad (1.3)$$

The equation above is known as the Monod model

Where

$\mu_{i,max}$ = maximum reaction rate
 K_m = Saturation constant of the micro-organism

To solve this set of differential equations, it is important to note that the values of k_m and $\mu_{i,max}$ must be determined for individual micro-organism. A solution of this will provide an approximate model for this process.

METHODOLOGY

Mathematical Model Development

In developing this model, several assumptions were made so as to simplify this complex process. One of the major assumptions is that the specific growth rate of the cells is exponential. This assumption leads to taking the Monod Model as an approximate model for the growth rate.

$$\mu_i = \frac{\mu_{i,max} S}{k_m + S} \quad (1.3)$$

From the experimental data by Brauman et al. (2002), the following were the cell number and the substrate concentration of the four major micro-organisms common in the mixed culture fermentation of palm juice. These four micro-organisms are *Yeast*, *Micrococcus*, *Lactic Acid bacteria (LAB)* and *Leuconostoc spp.* (LEU). The result is given below.

Table 2.1: Change in Cell number and Substrate Concentrate of the Individual Micro-organism with Time

Time (hr)	Yeast	Micrococcus	Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB)	Leuconostoc spp (LEU)	Substrate Concentrate (g/100g of dry matter)
0	312316	222246	10000	1584.89	6.5
24	1E+09	1E+07	1E+07	1000.00	6.3
48	1E+12	1.4 E+08	6.31 E+07	1000.00	2.2
60	1E+12	2.9 E+09	2.51 E+08	7328.55	1.6
72	1 E+13	50 E+09	30 E+09	15848.93	1.252

Source: Brauman et al. (2002)

A plot of substrate concentration against time was made in order to have an approximate value for the substrate concentration from 0 to 72 hours at 2 hours interval using the equation below.

$$y = 8.0385e^{-0.0256x}$$

Fig 2.1: Plot of Substrate Concentration against time at 2hrs interval

The cell numbers of the microorganisms is gotten from the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Yeast: } y &= 23465e^{0.2673x} \\ \text{Micrococcus: } y &= 50383e^{0.1703x} \\ \text{Lactic Acid Bacteria, LAB: } y &= 31486e^{0.1601x} \\ \text{Leuconostoc spp, LEU: } y &= 780.88e^{0.0316x} \end{aligned}$$

The cell growth rate of the individual microorganisms can be estimated using

$$\mu_i = \frac{\ln(N_f) - \ln(N_i)}{t_f - t_i} \quad (2.1)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} N_f &= \text{cell number of an organism at time, } t_f \\ N_i &= \text{cell number of an organism at time, } t_i \\ \mu_i &= \text{Specific growth rate} \end{aligned}$$

The calculation is done for each of the micro-organisms and shown in the table below.

Table 2.2: Cell Growth rate of Microorganism with Time

Time (hrs)	μ_{yeast}	$\mu_{\text{micrococcus}}$	μ_{LAB}	μ_{LEU}
0	0	0	0	0
24	0.4323	0.25455	0.28783	-0.01918
48	0.2878	0.10996	0.07675	0
60	0	0.25256	0.11510	0.16598
72	0.19188	0.04540	0.20673	0.06428

Kinetic Constant Estimation

It is important to determine the kinetic constants for the individual micro-organism in order to get an appropriate functional expression form for the Monod Models. The techniques used in achieving this include

- 1 Lineweaver-Bulk Plot
- 2 Eadie Hoftee Plot
- 3 Hanes Plot

The choice of choosing which technique to use is dependent on the nature of the process. The aim is to obtain a linear form of the Monod model and an estimate of the kinetic constant.

The kinetic parameters of Yeast, Leuconostoc spp., and Lactic acid bacteria was determined using Lineweaver-Burk plot from a plot of $1/\mu$ against $1/S$. Micrococcus was determined using Hanes plot from a plot of S/μ against S . The plots are shown below.

Fig 2: Plot of the Kinetic parameter for the four (4) microorganisms

Table 2.3: Kinetic Parameter for Individual Micro-organisms with Time

	Km (g/100g)	μ_m (hr ⁻¹)
Yeast	6.668	1.243
Micrococcus	0.17	0.2553
Lactic Acid bacteria, LAB	9.8384	0.588
Leuconostoc spp, LEU	-1.7338	-0.0139

Yield Coefficient

The yield coefficient of the four microorganisms is calculated from equation 3.1 using the formula below.

$$\text{Yield coefficient} = \frac{\Delta X}{-\Delta S} = \frac{X_f - X_i}{S_i - S_f} \quad (2.2)$$

Where

- X_f = the cell number of a particular organism at time, t_f
 X_i = the cell number of a particular organism at time, t_i
 S_i = the substrate concentration at time, t_i
 S_f = the substrate concentration at time t_f

Table 2.4: Yield Coefficient of the Individual Micro-organism with Time

Time (hrs)	Substrate	Yeast	Micrococcus	LAB	LEU
0	6.5	0	0	0	0
24	6.3	5.0E+09	5.0E+07	5.0E+07	-2924.45
48	2.2	2.436E+11	8.67E+07	1.3E+07	0
60	1.6	0	4.6E+09	3.13E+08	29298.84
72	1.252	2.586E+13	6.03E+09	7.9E+09	24481.178

We plot the respective yield coefficients of the microorganisms with respect to time using Microsoft Excel. The plots are shown below.

The respective equation from the graphs is given below. This equation is used to generate the yield coefficient of the individual microorganisms at 2 hours interval.

For yeast

$$Y_1 = 5E+08x^3 - 4E+10x^2 + 7E+11x - 2E+11$$

For Micrococcus

$$Y_2 = 17564x^3 + 522623x^2 - 4E+07x + 8E+07$$

For Lactic Acid Bacteria, LAB

$$Y_3 = 140287x^3 - 1E + 07x^2 + 2E + 08x - 6E + 07$$

For Leuconostoc spp

$$Y_4 = -0.2316 x^3 + 35.83x^2 - 1004.2x + 623.6$$

MODEL

The appropriate model for the process is as follows:

$$\frac{dX_1}{dt} = \mu_1 X_1 = \frac{1.243 \times S}{6.668 + S} \times X_1 \quad (2.3)$$

$$\frac{dX_{21}}{dt} = \mu_2 X_2 = \frac{0.2553 \times S}{0.017 + S} \times X_2 \quad (2.4)$$

$$\frac{dX_3}{dt} = \mu_3 X_3 = \frac{0.588 \times S}{9.8384 + S} \times X_3 \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{dX_4}{dt} = \mu_4 X_4 = \frac{-0.0139 \times S}{-1.7338 + S} \times X_4 \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{-\mu_1 X_1}{Y_1} - \frac{\mu_2 X_2}{Y_2} - \frac{\mu_3 X_3}{Y_3} - \frac{\mu_4 X_4}{Y_4} \quad (2.7)$$

Where X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , and X_4 are the initial cell numbers of the individual microorganisms

Numerical Solution to the Model

$$F_1 = \frac{dX_i}{dt} = F(X_1, S) \quad (2.8)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{dX_2}{dt} = F(X_2, S) \quad (2.9)$$

$$F_3 = \frac{dX_3}{dt} = F(X_3, S) \quad (2.10)$$

$$F_4 = \frac{dX_4}{dt} = F(X_4, S) \quad (2.11)$$

$$F_5 = \frac{dS}{dt} = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, S) \quad (2.12)$$

The differential equations can be solved by MATLAB which provides functions called solvers that implement Runge Kutta methods. The solver ode 45 uses a combination of fourth and fifth order Runge kutta. Therefore the solver ode 45 is used to solve the differential equations from 0-72 hours.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the mathematical models are approximate values based on the assumption that the relationship between the increases in the cell number of a micro-organism is exponential with respect to the equivalent usage of substrate. The mathematical model is useful, in that it shows considerable relation of the cell growth trend in the fermentation process. The initial substrate concentration of the medium is 6.5g/100g dry matter and the corresponding values of X1, X2, X3 and X4 for the respective micro-organism in succession that they occur are 31231.6 cells, 2222.4 cells, 10000 cells, 1584.89 cells respectively. An exponential yield coefficient for each of the micro-organism was estimated as

$$\begin{aligned} Y1 &= 5E+08X^3 - 4E+10X^2 + 7E+11X - 2E+11 \text{ cells/g substrate} \\ Y2 &= 17564X^3 + 522623X^2 - 4E+07X + 8E+07 \text{ cells/g substrate} \\ Y3 &= 140287X^3 - 1E+07X^2 + 2E+08X - 6E+07 \text{ cells/g substrate} \\ Y4 &= -0.2316X^3 + 35.83X^2 - 1004.2X + 623.6 \text{ cells/g substrate} \end{aligned}$$

From this inputs, the result on the MATLAB plots at 24 hours of the fermentation process, the cell number of Leuconostoc has increased to 1978.3 while the experimental value at this time is 1667.068, the equivalent substrate concentration at this point is 4.968g/100g dry matter while its experimental value is 4.348g/100g dry matter. This shows that there is reasonable level of accuracy in the model developed. The result also suggests that towards the end of the fermentation process, the cell number of the individual micro-organism remains constant while the substrate concentration continued depleting.

Fig 3: MATLAB Plots for substrate and the four microorganisms against time

CONCLUSION

Four micro-organisms were found to be frequently present during the mixed culture fermentation of palm-juice, these micro-organisms in the order of succession are; *Yeasts*, *Micrococcus*, *Lactic Acid bacteria* and *Leuconostoc spp*; it has also been shown that the fermentation process is acidic as it progresses and there is proliferation of micro-organisms depending on what the condition of the medium is. Kinetic parameters for the various organisms were estimated based on experimental data from literature. The yield coefficient of the individual microorganism was obtained. The yield coefficient was found to be exponential from 0 to 72 hrs. This is because the yield coefficient goes through a lag phase before it increases. A mathematical model has also been developed which represents the relationship of the microbial cell number and the substrate concentration with time. A computer program was also developed which solves and helps in simulating the model from 0 to 72 hours.

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NOTE: The following authors were cited in the content but not listed out as references

Okafor, 1978; Microsoft Encarta, 2004; Faparusi, 1966;

APPENDIX A

Function file

```
function dxdt = simulationifeoma (t, x)
```

```
% for Yeast
```

```
Y1= (5*(10^8)*(t^3)) - (4*(10^10)*(t^2)) + (7*(10^11)*t) - (2*(10^11));
```

```
% for Micrococcus
```

```
Y2= (17564*(t^3)) + (522623*(t^2)) - (4*(10^7)*t) + (8*(10^7));
```

```
% for Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB)
```

```
Y3= (140287*(t^3)) - (1*(10^7)*(t^2)) + (2*(10^8)*t) - (6*(10^7));
```

```
% for Leuconostoc spp
```

```
Y4= (-0.2316*(t^3)) + (35.83*(t^2)) - (1004.2*t) + 623.6;
```

```
dx1dt= ((1.234*x(5))/(6.668+x(5)))*x(1);
```

```
dx2dt= ((0.2553*x(5))/(0.017+x(5)))*x(2);
```

```
dx3dt= ((0.588*x(5))/(9.8384+x(5)))*x(3);
```

```
dx4dt= (((-0.0139*x(5))/(-1.7338+x(5)))*x(4);
```

```
dx5dt= -(((1.234*x(5))/(6.668+x(5))*x(1))/Y1)-(((0.2553*x(5))/(0.017+x(5))*x(2))/Y2)-...
```

```
(((0.588*x(5))/(9.8384+x(5))*x(3))/Y3)-(((0.0139*x(5))/(-1.7338+x(5))*x(4))/Y4);
```

```
dxdt=[dx1dt;dx2dt;dx3dt;dx4dt;dx5dt]
```

Script File

```
[t ,x]= ode45('simulationifeoma',[0:2:72],[31231.6 22224.6 10000 1584.89 6.5])
```

```
% cell number of Yeast
```

```
X1=x (:,1)
```

```
% cell number of Micrococcus
```

```
X2=x (:, 2)
```

```
% cell number of Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB)
```

```
X3=x (:, 3)
```

```
% cell number of Leuconostoc spp
```

```
X4=x (:, 4)
```

```
% substrate
```

```
Substrate=x (:, 5)
```

```
Plot (t, X4), xlabel ('time(hours)'), ylabel ('change in cell number'),... title ('plot of change in Leuconostoc spp against time')
```